

Blockchain-based e-government in Developing Economies: Public Trust, Legislation, Transparency and Social Dynamics

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Abstract

Background: While emerging distributed ledgers like DAG and Hashgraph gain prominence, blockchain technology remains a critical tool for enhancing transparency, accountability, and public trust in the government sector. In developing economies, where institutional trust is often fragile, these technologies offer significant potential to reform electoral integrity, public service delivery, and digital identity management.

Objective: This study evaluates the capacity of blockchain to support effective and fair digital governance. It specifically examines the interaction among technological features, legislative obstacles, and social dynamics that influence adoption in developing contexts.

Methodology: A systematic analysis of international literature (2020–2025) was conducted, complemented by a qualitative comparative and interpretative analysis of empirical cases from Romania and Canada. The research triangulates technological trends with legal regulations and socio-behavioural responses to assess implementation outcomes.

Results: Findings demonstrate that when embedded in clear institutional designs supported by cybersecurity and interoperability, blockchain significantly improves administrative transparency and reduces corruption vulnerabilities. Case studies highlight successful implementations in election monitoring in Romania and public finance in Canada. However, critical challenges persist regarding General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance—specifically, the "right to be forgotten",—scalability, and public acceptance.

Conclusion: Blockchain and new distributed technologies are valuable tools for modernising public administration, but require robust legislative support, digital education, and ethical

governance. For sustainable integration, these technologies must be accompanied by compatibility with international standards and a focus on maximising benefits for citizens.

Unique Contribution: This research provides a transdisciplinary perspective, bridging technology, law, and society. It synthesizes public policy lessons by comparing blockchain with other distributed technologies, offering a strategic framework for countries undergoing digital transition.

Key Recommendation: The study recommends implementing well-monitored pilot projects and proactive legislative adjustments, such as the creation of regulatory sandboxes. Furthermore, digital inclusion campaigns and the establishment of a legal regime that recognises the evidential value of digital records are essential to maximise technological impact in e-government.

Keywords: Blockchain, e-government, public trust, electronic voting, transparency, digital identity, regulation.

Introduction

E-government is already at the heart of public-sector modernisation, used to deliver services efficiently and to engage citizens in the digital environment. In developing economies, where public trust in institutions is fragile and abuse or political interests remain an issue, blockchain seems more suited to improving government transparency and accountability (Khalfan et al. 2022). As a technology, it is recognised for its immutability and decentralisation properties, which can prevent retroactive modification of data and enable a verifiable public record of transactions.

These characteristics are particularly attractive for e-government, as they strengthen citizens' trust that administrative processes and public decisions are transparent and free from manipulation. For these reasons, more and more countries are experimenting with the use of blockchain in areas such as electronic voting, property registries, public procurement and digital identity systems, with the expectation that it will bring integrity and efficiency to the public sector (Bustamante et al., 2022). Although it has been tested to date, the application of blockchain in governance still raises important questions regarding the adaptation of the legal regime, the protection of personal data and how citizens and public officials adapt to these new technological systems. The study addresses these multidimensional aspects of vulnerability, from public trust, law and transparency to social dynamics, assessing the extent to which blockchains can support e-governance in developing economies and the associated challenges.

The main objective of the study is to examine the potential of blockchain technology in the e-governance of developing economies, focusing on four critical dimensions: (1) increasing public trust in institutions through enhanced transparency and security of public data, which is so badly needed; (2) implications for the legislative and regulatory framework, more specifically how laws and policies need to be adapted (see the area of data protection and the legal validity of blockchain records); (3) improving transparency and accountability in the provision of public services such as voting, property registers, public procurement and digital identification; and (4) the impact on social dynamics, including civic participation, citizens' acceptance of technology and how it affects the relationship between the population and the

authorities. The problem that the study aims to solve is the lack of an integrated overview of how blockchains can transform public governance in the context of developing countries, where the need for transparency and accountability is acute, but where technical and institutional constraints unfortunately hamper implementation. The study aims to identify both the opportunities and risks associated with the adoption of blockchain in e-government, based on an analysis of recent literature and relevant practical examples.

Methodology

To achieve the proposed objectives, the research was based on a systematic analysis of the literature and an examination of recent case studies (from the last 5 years) on the implementation of blockchain in the public sector. High-impact academic publications and reports from international organisations were selected, with a focus on works published between 2020 and 2025, in order to cover the latest developments and discussions in the field. Studies directly addressing topics such as secure electronic voting on blockchain, digitised public services, such as land registries, public procurement, and blockchain-based digital identification systems, particularly in developing or transition economies, were included. The method consisted of identifying the main themes and trends in the reviewed works, starting with the anticipated benefits (e.g. reducing corruption, increasing trust and efficiency) to the challenges observed (e.g. technical problems, legislative obstacles, social resistance). The research compared initiatives from different countries, analysing efforts to implement electronic voting in Romania, pilot projects on transparency in public finance in Canada, land registry initiatives in African and Asian countries, and the development of sovereign digital identities in Europe. To validate the conclusions, source triangulation was used, corroborating data from scientific articles with government reports and official statements, in order to obtain a balanced and credible picture of the subject. For these reasons, the methodology is predominantly qualitative (conceptual and comparative analysis), but quantitative indicators mentioned in studies were also taken into account when considering the percentage increase in transparency or the level of citizen participation, where relevant. Given the evolving nature of the topic, the present methodology leads to a comprehensive synthesis of current knowledge, highlighting both achievements and gaps that require further research.

Results

By way of introduction, before moving on to the results, some comparisons between relevant technologies are presented. Blockchain technology, although increasingly challenged by new distributed ledger products such as Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAG), Hashgraph and Holochain, remains a central tool in debates on modernising governance by strengthening transparency, accountability and public trust. Although all these technologies share the principle of decentralised recording, their technical differences directly influence their suitability for public administration. They support citizens' rights to transparent governance, verifiable electoral processes, secure delivery of public services and protection of personal data, while imposing obligations on institutions regarding cybersecurity, register integrity, equitable digital access and independent auditing.

Comparative analysis shows that traditional blockchain excels in transparency and probative robustness, but still faces scalability limitations and high energy consumption in Proof-of-Work models. DAG provides nearly unlimited scalability and low costs, Hashgraph achieves

exceptional performance and consensus finality, and Holochain maximises privacy and scalability through agent-centric validation. No technology is perfect, so the balance between benefits and risks is paramount. In Romania, and in federal-provincial systems such as Canada, these types of technologies have the potential to transform electronic voting, digital public services and identity management, provided that technical performance is supported by neutrality, legislative adaptability and ethical governance.

Comparative Analysis of DLT Technologies

Figure: 1 is the result of the authors' comparative analysis.

1. *Increasing transparency and public trust through blockchain.*

The study results highlight a consensus in the literature that blockchain has the potential to significantly increase transparency in government processes, which can implicitly lead to increased citizen trust. A 2025 analysis emphasises that integrating blockchain into governance systems reduces corruption and strengthens public trust in institutions. Through its decentralised and immutable nature, blockchain maintains a permanent and incorruptible public record of government transactions and events. Canada has piloted a system for publishing research grant data on a public Ethereum blockchain, enabling citizens to directly verify the allocation of public funds in real time. The experiment demonstrated that the technology brings an unprecedented level of transparency to public finance management,

allowing constituents to participate in the verification and validation of government information. Improved transparency has a direct effect on trust: when citizens know they can independently verify government actions, their perception of institutional integrity increases. From this perspective, blockchain – s strengthens trust capital between states and citizens, especially in countries where this relationship has traditionally been marked by suspicion. However, the literature also highlights significant risks, such as the fact that the immutable nature of blockchain may conflict with GDPR rights, such as the ‘right to be forgotten’, and that decentralised governance often brings ambiguity in responsibilities and difficulties in law enforcement (Voloder & Reggianini, 2025).

2. Blockchain-based electronic voting – electoral integrity and challenges.

Empirical evidence suggests that while blockchain-based solutions may enhance transparency in electoral processes, their deployment in electronic voting systems remains experimental. Romania provides a relevant case in this regard, as blockchain technology was officially used to monitor voter turnout and data integrity during national elections, increasing transparency and public confidence in reported results (Stănescu, 2023).

At the same time, recent studies emphasise that blockchain alone cannot fully guarantee electoral integrity. Technical vulnerabilities, cybersecurity risks and the need to preserve voting secrecy remain critical challenges. Comprehensive reviews of blockchain-based e-voting architectures stress the importance of cautious implementation, independent auditing and hybrid approaches that combine distributed ledgers with traditional electoral safeguards (Ohize et al., 2025).

3. Improving public services and reducing corruption.

One of the most documented applications of blockchain in public services concerns land registration, particularly in contexts where weak institutions and corruption affect property rights. Blockchain-based land registries aim to create tamper-proof and publicly verifiable records, reducing discretionary power and opportunities for fraud. Georgia represents a well-documented case, where blockchain was used to secure property titles and improve transparency in land administration, contributing to increased legal certainty and public trust (Kshetri & Rogers, 2021).

Beyond land registries, blockchain has also been explored as a tool to enhance transparency in public procurement. Given that procurement represents a significant share of public expenditure in many countries, opacity in tendering procedures can facilitate corruption and inefficiency (OECD, 2022). Distributed ledger technologies enable the recording of procurement data in an immutable, traceable manner, ensuring that modifications to tender criteria or bids remain publicly visible and auditable. According to international policy analyses, such transparency mechanisms can strengthen accountability and discourage corrupt practices by expanding oversight beyond public authorities to include civil society and the media (World Economic Forum, 2020).

Overall, the literature indicates that blockchain-based public services can reduce administrative burdens, increase procedural transparency, and support more accountable governance, provided that implementations are embedded within clear institutional and legal frameworks.

4. *Digital identity integration and data protection.*

Another critical component of blockchain-based e-government highlighted by the results is citizens' digital identities. Many developing or transition economies lack robust population identification systems, which hinders people's access to public services and social protection schemes. Blockchain, particularly through the concept of self-sovereign identity, offers the opportunity to create digital identity ecosystems in which individuals can control their personal data, enabling institutions to verify identity attributes securely and in a decentralised manner. Recent literature indicates a clear trend: countries worldwide are exploring blockchain for digital identity. India has experimented with integrating its national biometric identity system, Aadhaar, with a blockchain platform to decentralise identity verification and enhance transparency in the use of identity data (López-Pimentel et al., 2025). The initiative aims to give citizens greater control over how their identities are used across contexts (banking, healthcare, voting, etc.), while reducing the risk of fraud and identity theft. The 2025 technical study proposes a digital identity ecosystem model based on unique government-issued tokens, combined with tokens issued by third parties (educational institutions, financial institutions, etc.) to create a verifiable identity tree. In this model, the government serves as a trusted authority that verifies basic identity, for example, by issuing a unique token to each person, akin to a digital ID card. And then the citizen can complete their digital identity with attributes certified by other issuers, such as a university degree, a driving licence, or property, all linked on the blockchain in a secure and transparent manner. The advantage of this system is that it enables a high degree of trust, as it is impossible to falsify as long as the issuing entities are trustworthy, while also providing confidentiality and control for the user, who decides which attributes to share and with whom. However, the implementation of digital identity on blockchain comes with some caveats that are clear from the results: guaranteeing the uniqueness and accuracy of data, resolving interoperability issues between different systems and countries, and the transaction costs associated with using blockchain on a national scale (one of the questions being who bears the cost of registration and verification on the blockchain?).

Legislatively, the integration of digital identity systems on blockchain requires states to re-evaluate how data protection and privacy laws apply to new technologies. The EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), for example, affords citizens the right to have their personal data deleted ('The right to be forgotten'). This concept appears to contradict the *immutability* principle of blockchain. The results suggest that either an adaptation of the technology is needed, through solutions such as off-chain storage of personal data, anchoring it on the blockchain through hashes, or the use of permissioned blockchains that can implement access controls, or legislative clarifications that allow for a balance between transparency and the right to privacy. In 2025, the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) (European Data Protection Board, 2025a) issued specific guidelines on the processing of personal data on blockchain, emphasising that blockchain technology is not exempt from GDPR compliance and that pseudonymisation of data on blockchain still falls under the regulations if individuals can be identified, even indirectly (European Data Protection Board, 2025b). Therefore, the widespread adoption of digital identities on blockchains in governance will require both technical and legal innovations to simultaneously protect citizens' security, so that their identity cannot be stolen or abused, and their privacy rights.

5. *Social dynamics and technology adoption.*

In addition to technical and legal considerations, the study's findings underscore the importance of social factors in the success of blockchain-based e-government projects. No matter how advanced the technology is, it will not produce the expected results if people, both public officials and citizens, do not understand and trust it. In developing economies, where digital literacy levels can be uneven, introducing blockchain into interactions with the administration requires awareness-raising and training efforts. Recent literature indicates that a lack of understanding and awareness of blockchain among public-sector staff can delay its adoption within institutions (Sousa, 2023). Indeed, if decision-makers and civil servants do not clearly perceive the benefits or fear the complexity of the new technology, initiatives are likely to stall. An example is the bureaucratic resistance sometimes encountered in digitisation projects, where officials perceive technology as a threat to the status quo or to their roles, especially when it involves trustless systems (which reduce reliance on trust in individuals).

Fig. 2 was developed by the author based on a synthesis of the results they arrived at.

On the other hand, citizens must also be convinced to use the new services. Public trust will not automatically transfer to the new system just because it uses a blockchain. On the contrary,

in the initial phase, people may be reluctant to create digital accounts or register their property/votes in a distributed ledger, especially if they do not understand how it works or fear for the security of their data. The results indicate that successful e-government projects have incorporated strong components of civic education and community engagement. Thus, in a 2023 study on *smart cities* and blockchain, researchers concluded that the use of distributed ledger technology in smart governance could significantly increase citizen participation in decision-making and improve the delivery of public services, provided that implementation is conducted transparently and inclusively (Testi et al., 2025). Blockchain can therefore facilitate civic engagement through consultative voting or participatory budgeting platforms where every vote is public and secure, but the positive effect depends on citizens' willingness to engage. A notable advantage of blockchain highlighted by the study is that it provides the possibility for forms of collaborative governance, such as in the monitoring of public procurement or local projects, where various actors in society (NGOs, the media, ordinary citizens) become 'nodes' of oversight, directly accessing and verifying data in the blockchain, which was much more difficult to achieve before. This changes the social dynamic, creating a more informed and proactive community that can flag irregularities or support decisions based on transparent data. However, it should be noted that in some cases, blockchain technology will not automatically be perceived as benign. Some social groups may express technological mistrust or even cultural resistance to new digital systems, interpreting them as imposed 'from above' or associated with foreign interests. The results therefore highlight the need for careful change management, in which states should accompany the implementation of blockchain with information campaigns, public consultations and pilot projects with a low initial impact, in order to demonstrate the benefits in a pragmatic way. Only in this way can the public buy-in be achieved and deeper digital divisions (where part of the population – often the most vulnerable – remains outside the system due to a lack of access or digital skills) be avoided. In conclusion, with respect to the social dimension, the results indicate that the success of blockchain-based e-government is not determined solely by technology; it is also linked to institutions' capacity to build trust and to support citizens and employees in adapting by developing a culture of transparency and accountability.

Unique Contribution of the Study

This paper makes an original contribution by integrating, within a unified framework, the multiple technological, legal, and socio-cultural aspects of blockchain implementation in e-government, with particular focus on developing economies. Unlike previous studies that have focused either on the technical aspects of blockchain in the public sector or on legislative implications or on isolated case studies, this study takes a holistic approach that links technological benefits to the dynamics of public trust and regulatory requirements. Its distinctive contribution lies in summarising the latest developments (over the last 3–5 years) in a dynamic field par excellence and highlighting lessons learned from various international initiatives. In particular, the study highlights how blockchain, beyond its risks, serves as a bridge between government and citizens, simultaneously through mechanisms to increase transparency (beneficial to the public) and efficiency tools (beneficial to the administration). By combining the example of Romania (the first EU country to adopt blockchain in the electoral process) with examples from other jurisdictions (Canada, Georgia, India, etc.), the research highlights the versatility and global applicability of blockchain, adapted to local particularities. The theoretical contribution of the study also lies in the conceptual formulation of the essential factors for success, such as transparency, integrity, participation, and obstacles,

such as the lack of a legal framework, resistance to change, and technical risks in blockchain-based e-government. This mechanism has the potential to guide both future research and decision-makers, providing a starting point for assessing the readiness of a developing country to implement blockchain in public administration. Therefore, from a practical point of view, the study provides informed recommendations for policy-makers and public project managers, showing where and how blockchain can bring benefits, whether we are talking about electoral processes, registries or procurement, and what accompanying measures are needed (i.e. legislative adaptations, training, public-private partnerships) for the sustainability and acceptance of these innovations. In short, the unique contribution of this paper is to clarify the potential of blockchain to positively transform the state-citizen relationship in developing economies, without idealising the technology, but approaching it critically and constructively, highlighting the conditions under which it can truly deliver tangible benefits.

Conclusion

The study concludes that, in terms of public trust, blockchain has positive features for transparency and accountability when public information, from votes to government financial transactions, is recorded immutably and accessible, and citizens gain confidence that things are being done correctly, which can rebuild trust in a state affected by corruption or inefficiency. The tangible benefits observed include increased integrity of electoral processes, reduced fraud and errors in public records, more efficient administrative services and more active community involvement in decision-making. The comparative analysis showed that these positive effects are not theoretical but have begun to be confirmed by real initiatives, ranging from blockchain-monitored elections in Romania to land registries in Georgia.

The conclusions underscore the message of caution that blockchain is not a panacea for governance problems. Its success is directly proportional to the complementary measures implemented. From a legal perspective, developing countries need to update their regulatory frameworks to integrate new digital realities, from the legal recognition of blockchain records (so that, for example, a certificate on the blockchain is as valid as one on paper) to alignment with international data protection and cybersecurity standards. Legislative gaps or ambiguities can undermine both the effectiveness and credibility of blockchain projects. From a technical perspective, issues such as network scalability, energy consumption, smart contract security and platform standardisation must be addressed before blockchain can be expanded nationally in a sustainable manner. Last but not least, the human factor is decisive, especially for countries adopting blockchain, which must invest in digital education for public employees and the population to ensure widespread adoption and proper use of new systems. Without this support, there is a risk that the technology will be underused or even rejected, maintaining the status quo.

Blockchain offers an opportunity to leapfrog stages and implement advanced governance mechanisms that may be more transparent and democratic than traditional ones. As shown above, it is designed as a trusted infrastructure to support modern public administration, where data and processes are verifiable by all stakeholders. However, this trust revolution will only take place if it is accompanied by a strategic vision and responsibility, namely the vision to rethink administrative processes around the principles of openness and collaboration enabled by blockchain, and the responsibility to manage risks carefully and put the citizens' interest at the centre of any technological implementation.

Key recommendations

Firstly, develop the regulatory framework by drafting or updating legislation that officially recognises blockchain documents and transactions (e.g., distributed electronic signatures, smart contracts, and digital records, as well as related operations). Compliance with international data protection standards (e.g., GDPR or equivalent) must be continuously monitored.

Next, pilot programmes and feasibility studies are welcome for gradual implementation through pilot projects in specific areas (as mentioned above, for example, a local land registry or an electronic voting system in a small community) to assess the performance of blockchain in real-world conditions and identify any issues. Programmes should be independently monitored and rigorously documented before being rolled out at the national level.

Another recommendation concerns investment in infrastructure and technical skills. To benefit from blockchain, developing economies need to invest in digital infrastructure, from broad internet access to decentralised storage and processing capacities and, above all, in skills training. Specialised training for government IT officials, hiring cybersecurity experts, and partnerships with academia/the private sector to manage and maintain DLT-based systems are also recommended

Any blockchain-based e-government initiative should include mechanisms for stakeholder consultation and participation, and impact assessment is recommended. It is also recommended that post-implementation studies and independent audits be conducted to assess the concrete impact of blockchain projects in government, e.g., on corruption rates, processing times, and citizen satisfaction. Issues such as the long-term sustainability of blockchain solutions, including costs and energy consumption, scalability in the context of growing government data volumes, and interoperability between different platforms and jurisdictions, remain open for further study.

References

- Bustamante, P., Cai, M., Gomez, M., Harris, C., Krishnamurthy, P., Law, W., Madison, M. J., Murtazashvili, I., Murtazashvili, J. B., Mylovanov, T., Shapoval, N., Vee, A., & Weiss, M. (2022). Government by code? Blockchain applications to public sector governance. *Frontiers in Blockchain*, 5, Article 869665. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbloc.2022.869665>
- European Data Protection Board. (2025a). *Guidelines 05/2023 on the use of blockchain technology in the context of personal data*. EDPB.
- European Data Protection Board. (2025b, April 8). *Guidelines 02/2025 on processing of personal data through blockchain technologies* (Version 1.1). https://www.edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2025-04/edpb_guidelines_202502_blockchain_en.pdf
- Khalfan, M., Azizi, N., Haass, O., Maqsood, T., & Ahmed, I. (2022). Blockchain technology: Potential applications for public sector e-procurement and project management. *Sustainability*, 14(10), Article 5791. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14105791>
- Kshetri, N., & Rogers, R. (2021, August 31). Blockchain-based property registries may help lift poor people out of poverty. *Government Technology*.

- <https://www.govtech.com/computing/blockchain-based-property-registries-may-help-lift-poor-people-out-of-poverty.html>
- López-Pimentel, J.-C., Gonzalez-Sanchez, J., & Morales-Rosales, L. A. (2025). A digital identity blockchain ecosystem: Linking government-certified and uncertified tokenised objects. *Applied Sciences*, 15(15), Article 8577. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app15158577>
- OECD. (2022, November 3). *Fair market conditions for competitiveness in the Adriatic region: Croatia country profile report*. OECD. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/fair-market-conditions-for-competitiveness-in-the-adriatic-region_916d18d0-en.html
- Ohize, H. O., Onumanyi, A. J., Umar, B. U., Edeko, F. O., Bamidele, F., & Edogbanya, O. G. (2025). Blockchain for securing electronic voting systems: A survey of architectures, trends, solutions, and challenges. *Cluster Computing*, 28, Article 132. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10586-024-04709-8>
- Sousa, M. J. (2023). Blockchain as a driver for transformations in the public sector. *Policy Design and Practice*, 6(4), 415–432. <https://doi.org/10.1080/25741292.2023.2267864>
- Stănescu, A. (2023, December 6). Blockchain tech in national elections: An experience from Romania. *Chambers*. <https://chambers.com/articles/blockchain-tech-in-national-elections-an-experience-from-romania>
- Testi, N., Marconi, R., & Pasher, E. (2023). Exploring the potential of blockchain technology for citizen engagement in smart governance. *Open Research Europe*, 3, Article 183. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16153.2>
- Voloder, E., & Reggianini, E. (2025, June 18). European Data Protection Board puts blockchain at a GDPR crossroads. *OMFIF*. <https://www.omfif.org/2025/06/european-data-protection-board-puts-blockchain-at-a-gdpr-crossroads/>
- World Economic Forum. (2020, June). *Exploring blockchain technology for government transparency: Blockchain-based public procurement to reduce corruption* (Insight Report). https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Blockchain_Government_Transparency_Report.pdf